

Communication Kit

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Abstract	The CRAFT-OA Communication Kit gives a summary of the visual identity of the project, material created for the means of dissemination and the overall communication approach.

Version and Revision History

Version	Date	Author/Reviewer/Contributors	Comments
0.1	4th July 2023	Sona Arasteh (MWS), Kristina Posavec (SRCE)	Draft
0.2	23rd July 2023	Barbara Svetina (ZRC SAZU), Kristina Posavec (SRCE)	Review
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List of Acronyms

CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
IPSPs	Institutional Publishing Service Providers
IPTPs	Institutional Publishing Technology Providers
HE	Horizon Europe
OA	Open Access
PALOMERA	Supporting the development of aligned policies for open access books and monographs”
PI	Principle Investigator
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Planning Organisation
RI	Research Infrastructure
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises

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Summary

This document serves as the communication toolkit for the project CRAFT-OA (**C**reating a **R**obust **A**ccessible **F**ederated **T**echnology for **O**pen **A**ccess). It outlines the project's identity and presents how it is represented in its key messages and visual identity. Furthermore, the document presents materials such as logos, templates and information material developed to support the communication and dissemination activities during the project run. Simultaneously, this document serves as a style guide for all consortium members.

1 Branding CRAFT-OA

Concerning the branding of CRAFT-OA four aspects will serve as the foundation of all communication and dissemination activities 1) the project identity, 2) key messages based on that project identity, 3) a list of keywords and 4) the close collaboration with other Horizon Europe (HE) projects. 'Branding' describes all activities, materials and actions that influence the project's reputation and its outputs.

1.1 Project Identity

As already referenced in the acronym CRAFT-OA, the core values of the project are pragmatism, trustworthiness, innovativeness and a close connection to the Diamond OA community. All actions and activities performed during the project are based on these core values. CRAFT-OA seeks to strengthen local and community-specific activities by upskilling, networking and horizontal integration.

1.2 Core Value and Key Messages

CRAFT-OA has developed two types of key messages: messages that reflect the core values of the project, core value messages, and stakeholder-tailored key messages with corresponding taglines. The latter derives from the stakeholder analysis conducted in CRAFT-OA deliverable 7.1 "[Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)" and aims to highlight aspects of the general key messages that cater to the needs and wants of specific stakeholders.

Core Value Messages

Core Value	Core Value Message
Openness	CRAFT-OA is dedicated to supporting and accelerating the transition to Diamond open access (OA) in the scholarly publishing system. In that regard, CRAFT-OA is upholding and promoting the vision of <i>open</i> scholarly publishing.
Pragmatism	CRAFT-OA is a hands-on project that tackles issues head-on. The project is committed to creating pragmatic technical solutions for OA publishers.
Innovativeness	New technical solutions need new ideas. CRAFT-OA is looking to create innovative technical solutions for Diamond OA publishing as well as innovative ways to share them among the community.
Equity	CRAFT-OA enables and supports equitable publishing as one of the core concepts of Diamond OA.
Community	CRAFT-OA is a community-driven and community-led project. It is a project <i>with</i> the community <i>for</i> the community. All project action is executed collaboratively with the Diamond OA

	community and all project results are to be taken up and developed further by the Diamond OA community.
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Stakeholder-tailored Key Messages and Taglines

Stakeholder	Message	Tagline
EOSC	CRAFT-OA helps promote the EOSC by integrating Diamond OA and other large-scale data aggregators.	Strengthen Europe’s position in the global Diamond OA ecosystem.
Citizen Scientists & Citizen Scientists PIs	By supporting the Diamond OA publishing model, CRAFT-OA serves as a strong advocate for the accessibility of research to everyone.	Only open research is for everyone.
Software developers	CRAFT-OA offers software developers the opportunity to actively engage in a project that promotes open-source software. Project results will be openly available for further development via software development, even after the funding period.	Be the backbone of progress.
Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs)	CRAFT-OA benefits IPSPs by a) offering technical solutions for Diamond OA publishing and b) by creating a community of practice that enables all actors in the Diamond OA	Be part of something bigger. Join the community.

	landscape to collaborate efficiently.	
Research Libraries	CRAFT-OA strengthens libraries by connecting them with community actors such as researchers and publishers.	Shape open access publishing; improve visibility, accessibility, and recognizability for Diamond OA publications.
Publishing Initiatives/Projects in Academia	CRAFT-OA delivers technical solutions available to all publishing initiatives and projects, thereby enabling them to set up open, equitable publishing.	Be part of something bigger. Join the community.
Research Infrastructures (RIs)	CRAFT-OA helps and supports RIs to consolidate a community of practice and contributes to them by setting up a technological infrastructure for OA publishing. Through participating in CRAFT-OA RIs help shape the future of OA publishing.	Shape OA publishing; Improve visibility, discoverability, & recognizability for Diamond OA publications.
Researchers	Researchers profit from CRAFT-OA and its outputs in several ways: a) improving the accessibility, discoverability, and recognizability of (their) research, b) providing tools and services for authors and editors.	Be part of something bigger. Join the community.
Research Planning Organisations (RPOs)/	CRAFT-OA promises to invest in the future of OA	Create Impact, invest in the future.

Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)	and in the sustainability of scholar-led publishing processes dedicated to FAIR principles as well as the publications themselves.	
Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) service providers in Diamond OA	Via CRAFT-OA SMEs gain an opportunity.	Be part of the future of OA.
Policymakers	By supporting CRAFT-OA policy makers help to steer the future of institutional publishing in the direction of open science.	Create Impact, invest in the future.

1.3 Keywords

A list of general keywords connected to CRAFT-OA was created to be used in day-to-day outreach endeavours:

scholar-led, scholar-driven, community, community-driven, community-led, FAIR, FAIR publishing, open science, visibility, discoverability, recognizability, OA publishing, Diamond OA.

1.4 Cross-Project Collaboration

CRAFT-OA works closely with fellow projects [DIAMAS](#) and [PALOMERA](#). The 40 partners of all three projects share one goal: to pave the way for an equitable future for scholarly communication with academic communities at the centre and thereby support community-led open scholarly publishing.

In matters of communication, all three projects are working on a common vocabulary based on the terminology developed in DIAMAS deliverable [2.1 IPSP Scoping Report](#). The cross-project communication vocabulary will assemble key messages and keywords all projects aim to convey, thereby supporting the alignment of communication and dissemination activities. The vocabulary will serve as a foundation for future communication about the Capacity Centre, DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA will contribute to.

2 Visual Identity

2.1 Logo, Favicon, Profile Picture

Logo

The project logo is the basic element of the CRAFT-OA identity. It is applied in visual project material and infrastructures (fact sheets, presentations, posters, website, and social media accounts) in order to ensure consistent branding across all communication tools and create an impact on its communities. As CRAFT-OA focuses on the integration of Diamond OA publishing with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the project logo for CRAFT-OA has been developed in a co-branding effort with the EOSC to highlight the close collaboration between both projects.

In all official contexts, especially vis-a-vis the commission all partners acknowledge the funding of the European Commission via displaying the EU emblem and the funding statement. As CRAFT-OA belongs to the EOSC-related projects and received respective funding, the CRAFT-OA logo is ideally used in combination with the EOSC lettering. In some specific contexts such as the use of the logo in national networks, discipline-specific networks or research infrastructures such as OPERAS, OpenAIRE or others, the CRAFT-OA lettering can be used without the EOSC lettering. For such exceptional use cases, the following style guide applies.

The logo is available to all consortium members in horizontal and vertical designs in four versions each to accommodate different backgrounds. The logos are available to third parties via a dedicated section of the project website.

The project logo aims for a plain, simplistic visual design to bear witness to the core value of pragmatism. The purple references the OPERAS' colours, and the font used, Roboto Regular, is a nod to the font affiliated with EOSC, Roboto Light. Roboto Regular features open curves and largely geometric forms. Both features symbolise the values of openness and pragmatism.

CRAFT-OA logo, for dark backgrounds

CRAFT-OA logo, for bright backgrounds

Co-branding logo, horizontal, for bright backgrounds:

Co-branding logo, vertical, for bright backgrounds:

Co-branding logo, horizontal, for dark backgrounds:

Co-branding logo, vertical, for dark backgrounds:

COLOUR CODES

purple: #662e6c; black: #000000; white: #fbfbfb; red: #952d42

Favicon & Profile Picture

A favicon and a profile picture have been created to support CRAFT-OA's social media appearance:

Favicon

Profile Picture

3 Presentation and Dissemination Material

To enable all members of the consortium to use a standardised visual appearance, a series of templates has been created, including templates for posters, deliverables, presentation slides and Zoom backgrounds.

Presentation Template

Zoom Background

Deliverable Template

DX.X Title of Deliverable										
Submission Date www.mm.dd.mm	Version X.X - Draft/Final									
Due Date www.mm.dd.mm	Please choose the level of dissemination according to GA: <table border="1"> <tr> <td>PU</td> <td>Public</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>SEN</td> <td>Sensitive</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>R-UE/UE-R</td> <td>EU classified</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	PU	Public		SEN	Sensitive		R-UE/UE-R	EU classified	
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The font used for the deliverables is Calibri.

Poster Templates

Fact Sheet

CRAFT-OA will develop a fact sheet that provides an overview of the project, its methodology and objectives and the benefits for its target communities. Project partners will translate the fact sheet to national languages to enhance dissemination through national channels and guarantee maximum efficiency.

4 Website

The project website, craft-oa.eu, is an essential communication tool for project dissemination activities. It provides up-to-date information about the project, its activities, liaisons, and outcomes. It serves as a gateway for the CRAFT-OA social media accounts as well as access to CRAFT-OA social media accounts and a subscription option to the project newsletter. The website structure will be gradually expanded and reorganised with new categories and content to reflect the project's progress, provide insights and effectively promote outcomes. While the website will grow over time, the overall structure of the website will be kept simple with only a few menu entries leading to subpages.

All partners are encouraged to provide content for the website about project activities that took place on a national level.

CRAFT-OA Homepage

5 Social Media

Two social media accounts were created for the project: a Mastodon account and an X (formerly Twitter) account. To ensure consistency and efficiency for all social media posts, a list of preferred hashtags has been assembled: #craftoa #diamondoa #openscience #horizoneurope. The Twitter account for CRAFT-OA is @craftoa_project, the Mastodon account is @craftoa@mastodon.online.

Whenever feasible, partner projects PALOMERA and DIAMAS will be tagged or mentioned to witness the close collaboration with these projects.

CRAFT-OA X profile

CRAFT-OA Mastodon profile